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Health sector reform in Honduras as privatization by coercion

ABSTRACT

I address the privatization of public health care services in Honduras by focusing on one family's experiences using both private and public health services. I juxtapose their increasing use of private health care services, over public services, against sustained and consistent episodes of health sector reform culminating in protests against decrees that sought to further restructure the Ministry of Health during early 2019. By complementing the concept of "privatization by attrition" with "institutional bad faith," I argue that the increased use of private health care may be understood as privatization by coercion.

KEYWORDS: Honduras, health reform, institutional bad faith, morbidity surveys, privatization by attrition, public health

Media teaser: How is the relationship between neoliberal health reform and neocolonialism experienced in Honduras? How does this relationship impact situated health decisions?

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In this article, I reflect on the slow process of privatization affecting the Honduran national health system (NHS). I introduce health sector reform processes in Honduras over the last three decades alongside intended legislative changes during 2019 that sought to transform the NHS to allow greater private sector involvement. These changes were widely opposed by the general population as they were considered a poorly veiled means to continue privatizing the NHS (Argueta 2019), while government representatives stressed that privatization was not the end goal, nor something that would occur (Álvarez 2019). Health sector reform in Latin America, guided by principles of efficiency and cost-effectiveness with the collaboration of benefiting private parties, has been shown to benefit private capital to the detriment of public institutions (Armada, Muntaner, and Navarro 2001). I address the visible spaces of exclusion that were generated and justified when government representatives declared, despite evidence to the contrary and popular condemnation, that privatization of the NHS was not a goal or even a reality.

I employ the concept of “privatization by attrition” (Verdugo 2004), to describe one family’s experiences (Rosalinda and her children) securing health care services. I adopt Verdugo’s insights alongside Gordon’s theorizations on “institutional bad-faith” (Gordon 1995). As an extension of individual bad-faith (the condition of lying to oneself and others about the world), Gordon argues that “institutional bad-faith” is a characteristic of racist institutions that seek to discourage “recognition” between individuals to maintain a pathological status quo (1995). I propose that Rosalinda’s experiences navigating the NHS amounted to privatization by coercion orchestrated through “institutional bad faith.”

Methods

Data were collected over the course of 14-months of ethnographic fieldwork in downtown Tegucigalpa, Honduras (April 2018 – June 2019). Primary data were collected through participant observation of daily conditions of life and through morbidity surveys (Das 2015)¹. I carried out the morbidity surveys with Rosalinda and her children on a weekly basis for 32 weeks (between April and November 2018); these could last between 30 minutes to three hours. During these surveys, I gathered information on any illnesses in the household during the week in question, symptoms that accompanied the illness, name of the illness, mode of diagnosis, and health seeking strategies adopted. After completing the morbidity surveys, I continued to visit Rosalinda on a weekly basis as a friend. I complemented primary data with secondary data from newspapers and popular television news outlets. The public gatherings and protests depicted here took place between 24 April 2019 and 6 May 2019.

Since one of my goals was to understand poor urban families' experiences using public and private health services, I engaged four other families in downtown Tegucigalpa while conducting research with Rosalinda and her family. Although all the other families I conducted research with over this period had similar experiences accessing both public and private health care services, I decided to focus on Rosalinda and her children because they used both these services most frequently. Rosalinda provided her informed consent to participate in research and provided her assent for both her children. I use pseudonyms for Rosalinda and her children. To obtain Rosalinda's informed consent and her assent for her children, I discussed the underlying rationale of the research along with the potential benefits and risks from participation. I provided Rosalinda with an information sheet with the same details, along with contact information for national and international academic institutions whom she could contact to obtain additional

information or report misconduct. I reminded Rosalinda frequently that her participation was voluntary and that she could end her participation at any point, as well as request that I erase any data that I had collected on her and her children. Once we developed rapport, Rosalinda shared information openly about her and her children's health episodes, as well as on other features of their daily lives. I obtained all my information on Rosalinda's children through Rosalinda. I limited my interactions with Rosalinda's children, like many of the adults that circulated around their sphere, to playing games and, in the case of Rosalinda's oldest, to brief chats regarding their current interest or latest adventure. Rosalinda gave me permission to audio record our interactions, but I quickly learned that Rosalinda spoke less, and less candidly, when she knew I was recording her. In response, I stopped recording our conversations and decided to focus on producing detailed notes after our encounters. Likewise, given the public nature of our encounters, which I detail below, I quickly learned around whom Rosalinda did not feel comfortable broaching certain topics or continuing certain conversations. I learned to follow Rosalinda's lead, which either punctuated our conversations throughout a period of several hours or simply meant the conversation would have to be taken up again another day or, in a few instances, abandoned altogether.

Health reforms, privatization by attrition, and institutional bad faith

Under the guise of modernization, many public health systems across Latin America were subjected to transformation processes intended to improve health service efficiency and efficacy (Carmenate-Milián et al. 2017; Cueto and Palmer 2014) under the double-pronged approach of decentralization and privatization (Homedes and Ugalde 2005). Many of these changes began to take place during the 1990s, when the World Health Organization (WHO) adopted institution-

wide operational plans to mimic the health service models being proposed by the World Bank (WB) (Adams 2013; Cueto 2013; Packard 2016), although some of these changes began to take place as part of structural adjustment programs (SAPs) imposed on Latin American countries by international financing institutions (IFIs) during the 1980s (Ansaldi and Giordano 2006; Armada, Muntaner, and Navarro 2001; Cueto and Palmer 2014). Under SAPs, Latin American countries were forced to open their economies to private transnational actors, drastically reduce public spending, and devalue their currencies (among other measures) to access development loans and funds (Ansaldi and Giordano 2006; Cueto and Palmer 2014; Gershman and Irwin 2000). One of the results of SAPs was to reduce the role of governments in the provision of public services and to increase the role of private service providers (Armada, Muntaner, and Navarro 2001; Gershman and Irwin 2000) under the assumption that the private sector would more efficiently and effectively manage a variety of services through competition in a free market (Ganti 2014). With encouragement from international financing institutions, multilateral organizations and other foreign donors, countries like Honduras undertook changes in the structure and operation of their NHS (Armada et al. 2001; Homedes and Ugalde 2005). These changes led to restructuring financial and service arrangements between the public sector and private interests, where public sector financing both subsidized private profits and transferred risk for speculative investments to the public sector through public-private partnerships (Laurell 2014; Birn et al. 2016). Research by Armada et al. (2001), Homedes and Ugalde (2005), and Verdugo (2004; n.d.) suggests that the reduction of public involvement and investment in health care service delivery and management, and the concomitant increase of private service delivery and management, negatively impact the status of health care systems and health care delivery, while generating vast wealth for transnational conglomerates and local elites. This process of capital accumulation

is characterized by reducing/cutting public expenditures in health and separating health service financing from health service provision in a bid to create a health service marketplace for private actors (Armada et al. 2001; Laurell 2014), two approaches highlighted as necessary to reform the Honduran NHS (SESAL 2009, 2013; Suazo 2011).

Verdugo (2004; n.d.) analyzed the process of decentralization and privatization in the Guatemalan public health sector by addressing the preponderance of IFIs and foreign donors in the design and execution of local health care reform. The WB and Interamerican Development Bank designed and forced the implementation of health reforms in Guatemala that facilitated the transition of the public system into private control with the approval of a benefitting local elite (Verdugo n.d.). Verdugo identified a redefinition of the role of the Guatemalan state vis-a-vis the provision and maintenance of health as a right towards the exploitation of health as a commodity, noting that “state modernization” was best understood as a process “to establish clear rules and stability for the private sector and market, while maintaining sufficient coercive measures to control growing social demands” (2004:63), in which subsidies were shifted towards “the creation and maintenance of conditions which allow the market and the private sector to flourish” (2004:66). For Verdugo (2004; n.d.), reforms in the Guatemalan health sector were designed to create wealth by redirecting the distribution of resources from the lower classes to local and transnational upper classes. In the process, public healthcare services were dismantled and replaced by “private nonprofit entities ... to meet basic public health and community needs” resulting in “privatization by attrition” (Verdugo 2004:59). Verdugo defines privatization by attrition as “reactions from private parties or from society meant to address health needs, given the state’s abandonment of this issue” (n.d.:2), or relying on non-public health services to satisfy health needs. These processes exemplified the “dilemma between consensus and coercion”

(Verdugo n.d.:1). Coercion is key for introducing Gordon's concept of "institutional bad faith" (1995:22)² in a way that both re-signifies the role of the human within the institutional and which identifies the explicit project of dehumanization on which colonial capitalist expansion depends (Bear 2020).

Gordon theorized "institutional bad faith" to explain how extraordinary events of violence perpetrated within racist societies become absorbed into a mundane and ordinary reality, turning commonplace to the extent of becoming (seemingly) invisible (1995:22-23, 38-39). Like "bad faith," which Gordon defines as "an effort to hide from one's freedom and responsibility" (1995:19) and ultimately connects to ways of relating to Others which are "misanthropic" (1995:19-20), "institutional bad faith discourages human recognition. It is an effort to construct collectives and norms ... that militate against sociality, against human being" (1995:22). Through "institutional bad faith," historically produced racist institutions (or varied ways of regulating social reality) aim to maintain and affirm existing conditions of inequality by presenting existing social conditions as natural or given and in need of protection, thereby justifying actions by individuals that work to protect the established order or limiting the sense of responsibility that individuals may have for altering a social reality assumed to be fixed (1995:22-23). "Institutional bad faith" ultimately normalizes the ordinary everyday violence suffered by distinct groups of people by attempting to erase the historical processes and actions that created the present moment (1995:23, 86) and through the fabrication of a dehumanized non-Other (produced under the oppressive conditions of colonialism) (Gordon 1995:57-61) who is denied "human recognition" and considered a natural target of said violence. That is, racist institutions encourage us to separate ourselves from the daily and persistent consequences of structural violence (e.g., unequal access to basic public services, institutional discrimination,

urban precarity and poverty, police brutality) suffered by Others by presenting those others as what Gordon describes as overdetermined others. Gordon argues that “overdetermination” is the “perversion of anonymity” (1995:58-59), which reduces individuals to stereotypes that respond to our own preconceptions making it impossible to acknowledge the unknown totality of the Other and consequently their status as an individual Other. As a result, the Other is always already known, seen to lack attributes of human being (such as an individual perspective and experience of the world), and fashioned as less-than-human (1995:60-61), which in colonial and racist societies serves to “shift the presuppositions of justice and fairness” (1995:81). In operational terms, “institutional bad faith sometimes takes the form ... of an attack on humanity in the name of humanity ... a discouragement of choice through the presentation of ossified values,” which become “tools of evasion” (1995:22) of responsibility. For my immediate purposes, reform, modernization, transformation, restructuring and efficiency are devices to establish social and temporal borders: social borders around those who would be seen to impede their fulfilment, constructed as “perverse” masses, and those whom their fulfilment would benefit; and temporal borders that mark off the past as irrelevant by stressing a focus on the present (1995:23, 86).

Current structure of the NHS, genesis, and a history of recent reforms

The Honduran NHS is composed of the Ministry of Health (MOH), the Honduran Institute of Social Security (IHSS), and private service providers (Rodríguez Herrera 2006). The MOH has 29 hospitals, three emergency attention centers, and 1,514 local public clinics (Carmenate-Milián et al. 2017:2). The IHSS has two hospitals that are managed directly, seven emergency attention centers, and 32 clinics managed through third parties (Bermúdez-Madriz et al. 2011:S214). The

private sector has 1,131 registered attention centers (Carmenate-Milián et al. 2017:2). The IHSS, and its associated centers, provide services to around 16.8 percent of the population, the MOH provides services to 60 percent of the population through its network, and around five percent of the population rely on private providers (INE and SESAL 2021:702). The Honduran NHS is mostly financed through out-of-pocket expenditures (Toledo Prieto et al., 2018) in the form of both direct payments and co-payments (ILO and PAHO 1999). Out-of-pocket expenses represented 46.5 percent of health sector financing in Honduras, per 2016 data (Toledo Prieto et al., 2018:1), which represented a substantial cost to service-users and is regarded as a source of inequality in the provision of health services (ILO and PAHO 1999), especially for populations laboring in the informal sector.

Genesis of the NHS and recent reforms

The public sector of the Honduran NHS was borne out of pivotal labor movements and struggles in the northern coast of the country; specifically, the workers' strike of 1954 (Martínez 2003; Williams 2009). The Ministry of Labor (MOL) and the MOH were created in 1955 as a direct result of this strike (Williams 2009). The statutes that gave birth to the MOL enshrined the provision of health and the maintenance of well-being as a necessary precondition for preserving the overall quality of life of workers in the country (Martínez 2003). In line with the statutes of the MOL, the IHSS was created in 1959 to provide medical attention, public pensions, and insurance schemes for dependent workers across the country (Williams 2009).

During the 1990s, some of the first modernization and reform projects were undertaken (PAHO 2009) following “new public management” models (Johnson 2010; Suazo 2011). Under the presidency of Rafael Callejas (1990 – 1994), Honduras signed a series of bilateral

agreements with the USA that focused, in part, on restructuring and reforming the Honduran NHS by modernizing hospital management and altering the pension and insurance scheme under the IHSS (Rodríguez Herrera 2006:19). These changes also focused on decentralizing health care services to reduce service provision from the MOH (PAHO 2009:32), under the notion that private service providers would lessen overall costs and improve service delivery by allowing health services to be managed locally through competition in a local health marketplace (Johnson 2010; SESAL 2013; Suazo 2011). The intended reforms did not take place to the extent envisioned owing both to local resistance and the lack of necessary financing to execute the transition (Suazo 2011). During the 1990s, international assistance to Honduras, primarily from the USA, diminished considerably (Castellanos 2005; Suazo 2011). However, towards the end of the decade, international aid increased again in response to the natural disaster occasioned by Hurricane Mitch in October-November 1998 (Castellanos 2005; PAHO 2009; Rodríguez Herrera 2006; Suazo 2011). With the increase in external aid, there was renewed attention on reforming and restructuring the NHS spearheaded by imposed conditionalities on foreign aid and loans (Castellanos 2005; PAHO 2009; Suazo 2011). The period from 1999 to 2006 saw the introduction of several experiments in health provision models and renewed attempts to separate public health sector financing from service provision (Castellanos 2005; Suazo 2011). Mainly, these experiments sought to provide evidence that the MOH would benefit from reducing its role to supervision and financing of healthcare services, as opposed to retaining a role in service provision, and that the IHSS would equally benefit from reducing their focus to pension and insurance provision by contracting third parties (both for profit and non-profit organizations) to organize and manage healthcare service delivery for its affiliates (Dowling Root et al. 2020; Rodríguez Herrera 2006; Suazo 2011). These experiments focused on the eventual

decentralization of the NHS and on the perceived need to introduce and carve out a space for private service providers to address larger health inequalities within the country (PAHO 2009:16).

Under the presidency of Manuel Zelaya (2006-2009), the administration continued processes for the reform and restructuring of the MOH and IHSS to satisfy existing and new (e.g., UN Millennium Development Goals) commitments with international donors (PAHO 2009; SESAL 2009; Suazo 2011). However, Zelaya's administration also sought to strengthen the role and financing capacity of the IHSS by extending pension and insurance coverage to previously uncovered domestic employees and by opposing legislation that sought to reduce worker's rights (PAHO 2009; Williams 2009). After the coup against Zelaya in June 2009 (CIDH 2009), the new government passed legislation in 2010 (La Gaceta 2010) introducing an employment by hour scheme, which removed employers' obligation to contribute to their workers' public pension and insurance schemes (Suazo 2011).

Starting in 2010, with the presidency of Porfirio Lobo (2010 – 2014), the National Health Plans, again, actively contemplated reducing the role of the MOH to a supervisory and comptroller capacity while once more highlighting the points of entry for the private sector (República de Honduras 2010; SEDS 2012; SESAL 2013). In February 2010, Decree 286-2009 became law, and laid out what would become the foundation for the latest iteration of decentralization processes currently affecting multiple Honduran public sectors³. Regarding the NHS, these decentralization measures were stipulated in several national health plans associated with the *Partido Nacional* (PN) in power from 2009-2021 (SESAL 2009, 2013, 2014), leading to a series of legislative changes from 2012 to the present (La Gaceta 2012, 2015, 2017, 2018, 2019) designed to outline the role of private service providers in the NHS, while at the same time limiting the functions

assigned to the MOH and the IHSS. This latest round of restructuring processes led to the continued fragmentation of public health services, the limited role of the MOH in controlling public expenditures in health, and the increased participation of the private sector in the delivery of essential public health services (Carmenate-Milián et al. 2017). According to Carmenate-Milián et al. (2017), this weakened public health service provision and turned other essential public health services virtually non-existent. In the national health plans associated with the second administration of president Juan Orlando Hernandez (2018-2022), the role of the MOH was reduced to a mostly supervisory capacity (SESAL 2014), while foregrounding a universal health coverage model (SESAL 2013:17) and “results-based governance” that incorporated “the concept of competition” (SESAL 2013:41) into the provision and administration of public services.

In 2016, Suyapa Figueroa and Samuel Santos, representatives of the Honduran Medical College (CMH), began to express their concern over the seemingly systematic way in which the executive branch, under Juan Orlando Hernandez, was attempting to privatize public health services through the *Ley Marco del Sistema de Protección Social* (Framing law for the Social Welfare System) (Radio Progreso 2016). The CMH held the position that this law “disappear[ed] public health” and turned health into a “privilege” (Carmenate-Milián et al. 2017:4). This law was approved in July 2015 on the heels of a well-publicized corruption scandal concerning the IHSS between 2010-2013 (La Gaceta 2015; La Prensa 2015; Montenegro 2015), in which PN members at the head of the institution embezzled public funds through a variety of means, including the approval of overpriced acquisitions for the public health sector from private sector providers, unverified services and goods procurement from private sector providers, and siphoning of public health monetary resources to sham non-governmental organizations (Morales, Leitzelar, and Salinas 2014). Figueroa and Santos were clear that there was a crisis in the public health care sector

and that the PN leadership had fabricated the crisis to justify the slow privatization of public health services (Radio Progreso 2016). In August 2018, the government declared another crisis in the public health sector (Confidencial 2018). Figueroa quickly issued statements and gave interviews declaring that the executive decree, which granted emergency powers to an intervening commission to overcome the perceived crisis, was another thinly veiled attempt to re-start the process of privatizing public health care services (Argueta 2019).

Most recent intended health reforms and media defense

On 25 April 2019, the Honduran legislature hastily approved two decrees to restructure both the Ministries of Health and Education⁴. Opposition party members in Congress fought to obstruct the vote on several grounds but were overruled (Ordóñez Baca 2019). The controversy surrounding the decrees related to how these would affect existing legislation that already regulated the way both ministries operated in terms of public sector financing; service procurement from the private sector; oversight functions intended to ensure quality of services and resources available to users; the operational structure of the ministries as increasingly decentralized institutions; and hiring and firing practices (El Heraldo 2019). The last point, especially, was considered by popular sector representatives as an affront to workers' rights legislation championed over the last 70 years, since it would inevitably lead to "mass firings" (Radio Progreso 2019; Villegas 2019). The next day, on 26 April 2019, civil society groups took to the streets in marches protesting the actions of both the executive and the legislative branches. The following week, civil society groups, primarily the large public teachers' and medical doctors' unions, took to the streets in protests that were quelled by police. Amid the precarity,

uncertainty, protests and state-led violence, the decrees that were passed on 25 April were annulled just five days later (La Tribuna 2019).

On appearances in news outlets during the days in question, government representatives, including the Minister of Health, primarily focused on dispelling the “misguided notion” that the decrees in any way opened the door to “mass firings” (Álvarez 2019). The overall intent of the decrees, according to the Minister of Health, Alba Consuelo Flores, was to guarantee that the MOH could begin to operate “more efficiently” and to streamline administrative procedures given current infrastructural and service needs, and “supernumerary” staff levels (Álvarez 2019). The Minister of Health further stressed that the purpose of the new legislation was to improve the “hiring and infrastructural procedures” within the ministry and to make “internal modifications within the [ministry’s] budget” that would make it possible to better perform its mandate, while stressing that the country could not afford to “steam roll the rights of the population at large, to whom we owe [our efforts]” (Álvarez 2019). The declarations made opposition representatives’ reservations surrounding the decrees sound unreasonable, and largely controlled the tone and content of the debate in private media outlets in a practised display of neoliberal “cooptation” (Birn et al. 2016). Meanwhile, what representatives of health and education worker’s unions were in fact calling for was greater transparency regarding what the decrees would change in terms of established procedure, greater accountability for failure to comply with already existing procedures and regulations, and a reconsideration of existing legislation that paved the way for the “privatization” of the existing public health care system (Álvarez 2019).

Rosalinda's Situated Experience

Rosalinda's and her children's experiences with the public health care system are illuminating for this discussion because they were invisibilized subjects in public policy determinations (Abrams et al. 2020; Crenshaw 1991) and victims of repressive neocolonial stratagems turned policy (Lugones 2008). As Gordon notes, "structures are *situationally* lived by people of flesh and blood" (1995:45, emphasis in original). Rosalinda, and the women around her, frequently talked about negative experiences using public health care services. These were poor women with children who interacted somewhat frequently with the public health system because of their children's health issues, as well as their own. These women may have experienced the deficits in the public health system before others, but they were certainly not the only subjects affected. For Rosalinda, the crisis could not be reduced to a particular moment or mode of service provision, but was composed by the slow and steady rhythms of poverty (Das 2015) and the seemingly unchanging realities of sanctioned inequality that continually exposed her and her children to adverse health episodes (Singer and Baer 1995).

Rosalinda as a local political actor

A few days after the events of 26 April 2019, I went to meet Rosalinda to talk about the protests and to get her perspective on the situation. When I got there, she was sitting on a stoop talking with two men about instances of police repression she had observed and experienced the day before. Rosalinda looked and sounded angry. As soon as I sat down across from her, she yelled out at me, "They want to increase [the cost of medical] consultations! They're going to change it to 80 *Lempiras*!⁵ If I can't even go right now that it's 5 [*Lempiras*], can you imagine when it's 80?" Rosalinda repeated the same figure in different iterations to different people throughout the

afternoon and her indignation never wavered. I spent most of the afternoon with Rosalinda, as protests and police repression continued to take place across downtown Tegucigalpa. I later sheltered in place at an apartment that belonged to one of Rosalinda's friends, while watching the live legislative session being broadcast on a local news channel. It was during that afternoon that the legislature was pressured to repeal the decrees discussed above during a special session.

Rosalinda and her children

I met Rosalinda in April 2018, when she was 34-years-old. Rosalinda lived and worked in one of the southwest margins of downtown Tegucigalpa. She made a living for herself and her two small children, 4-year-old Carlos and 1-year-old Manuel, by selling assorted snacks and sweets on a street corner across from where she lived. The corner where Rosalinda worked was not particularly busy. It was more than seven blocks away from the busier parts of downtown, but it was close to home and a thoroughfare for pedestrians. Rosalinda was a single parent and making a living in a way she could easily and comfortably watch over her small children was one of her priorities.

During April 2018, Rosalinda rented a room for herself and her two small children in an auto-repair shop. By April 2019, she had moved half a block down the street to a wide, mostly empty lot that the owner rented out to a tyre-repair shop, a live-stock operation (a wooden pig pen with 12-14 pigs about 10 meters away from the closest temporary shelter), and to several other poor families. The auto repair shop where Rosalinda used to live when I met her took up a street corner. A cinder block wall at least five meters high surrounded the shop, the wall in turn supported a roof of thick decaying wooden beams covered with gabled zinc sheets. Makeshift wooden columns were placed throughout the shop floor to hold up the beams that no longer

provided any support to the roof. The walls of Rosalinda's room were made from wooden planks about two meters high. Rosalinda tried to cover the gap between the walls to her room and the ceiling by using bed sheets, and only really managed to cover the space half-way. Rosalinda's queen mattress occupied most of the room. She had a small gas stove, a dresser, and a 12-inch TV. Rosalinda had lived in that room with her sons Manuel and Carlos for three years.

Rosalinda usually started her routine at 8:00 a.m. and would set up shop on the corner across the street by 11:00 am every day, except on Sundays. She would set-up her merchandise on three wooden crates in front of a low-lying stoop under a concrete awning, which provided protection from the sun. Rosalinda would usually stay on her corner until the sun went down, between 5:30 and 6:00 p.m., but occasionally she would pack things up earlier if sales were slow. Manuel and Carlos were usually around, playing together and with other local children, or just being coddled by the numerous adults who stopped by on a regular basis to say “Hi” to Rosalinda. Sometimes a friend or a neighbor would offer to take care of the youngest, Carlos, and sometimes Manuel would stay in the room watching TV. When I started my visits, there were usually two or three people from the auto-repair shops hanging out at the corner on any given day, but as business started to sour in late 2018 and early 2019, people employed in the shops were forced to find jobs elsewhere. Rosalinda's business also began to suffer; she went from making around US\$12 a day in mid-2018 to making as little as US\$4 a day by early 2019.

Rosalinda's experience with the public health system

During the first three months I knew Rosalinda, she made frequent use of health care services available at the local public health center (CS) managed by the MOH, and generally had quite positive things to say about the services and their delivery. However, by July 2018, her opinion

of the CS had deteriorated, and she increasingly relied on private health care services for both herself and her children. A possible reason for this shift is described in more detail in the following sub-section. Rosalinda was especially fond of a private clinic run by doctor Martín, who, for around US\$6, would provide a consultation, a diagnostic, and pharmaceuticals. I later found out doctor Martín was rather well-known downtown for his services and had a steady clientele, in spite of the stiff competition. There were at least six low-cost private clinics in the same five-block radius. Rosalinda's first choice to obtain treatment had, at one point, been the CS because it was cheaper. As the months went by, and both Rosalinda and her children suffered from sustained and frequent illnesses, Rosalinda began to re-evaluate the overall invisible costs of accessing public health care services. The time she invested procuring public health care services off-set the low user-fees and the, increasingly less, guaranteed access to medication. Rosalinda also believed that the *trato/tratamiento* she was increasingly receiving in the CS exposed her to discrimination. In English, *trato/tratamiento* translates as *treatment*, referring both to someone's behavior and disposition towards someone else (*trato*), and medical services provided to a patient (*tratamiento*). Rosalinda believed the somewhat stable access to *tratamiento* would probably force her to keep using public health care services, but the *trato* she received made it less likely if other options were available. As *tratamiento* became harder to access within the public health care system, Rosalinda relied increasingly on private sector services.

Some of the first weekly conversations on health I had with Rosalinda addressed Carlos's dental issues and Manuel's gastrointestinal afflictions. Carlos would constantly complain about tooth pain in the back of his jaw, and Rosalinda would tell me how difficult it was for Carlos to eat or sleep. Carlos's complaints, according to Rosalinda, were usually accompanied by a low-grade fever and sometimes diarrhea. From May to mid-June 2018, she visited the CS with one of

her sons almost on a weekly basis, during the weekends. During these visits, Rosalinda sought consultations with the resident pediatric dentist whom she thought was patient and kind with Carlos. During the initial visit I documented, the dentist suggested the extraction of one of Carlos's molars but scheduled the extraction for the following week, because of an infection. Rosalinda usually came back from the public clinic with medications (invariably, trimethoprim sulfamethoxazole and amoxicillin), although, on occasion, she came back with a script of medications to purchase at a private pharmacy. Each week after that, Rosalinda would tell me how the dentist kept suggesting a tooth extraction to deal with the cavity on Carlos's molar; an approach documented as common in poor, racialized contexts elsewhere (Horton and Baker 2010). Each passing week the dentist would also inform Rosalinda that the site was still too infected and swollen to perform the extraction. On Carlos's last visit to the CS, after a round of antibiotics, when the molar extraction finally looked like a possibility, Carlos simply made it impossible for the dentist to extract his molar by refusing to sit still for the local anesthetic injection.

During the same period, Manuel suffered from frequent bouts of diarrhea and high fevers and continued to have frequent episodes of diarrhea throughout 2019. Rosalinda took Manuel to the public clinic as often as she would take Carlos for his follow-up visits, but she believed that Manuel's stomach issues were most likely related to *mal de ojo*⁶ or *empacho*⁷. Although she continued to administer the medications that the CS provided, she would also hedge her bets on Manuel's health by visiting a local *sobador*⁸ or by having a relative perform the massages.

Public health care failure: Indifference, charity, and private practice

In mid-June 2018, Manuel did not react as expected to one of the *empacho* treatments and Rosalinda decided to go to the CS to get a second opinion. “Wouldn’t you believe that they had me waiting for like two hours? And I had this kid with me that was burning-up and crying,” recounted Rosalinda. “Were they that busy?” I asked. “No,” she replied, and continued, “It’s just that those nurses just hang around doing nothing! I got mad at one of them and told her, *Oigame*, why hasn’t anyone checked me in? Can’t you see that my son is very sick?” The nurse that overheard Rosalinda was offended by her comment and retorted that “mothers like her” only knew how to complain and that Manuel’s fever was nothing serious. Rosalinda answered back by saying “Do your job!,” prompting the nurse to come over. She inspected Manuel perfunctorily, told Rosalinda he was just running a fever, and again failed to perform the necessary intake procedures to get Manuel on the list to see a doctor. It took another hour for Rosalinda to gain access to the doctor. After a short examination, they prescribed an antibiotic that was unavailable at the public clinic, which Rosalinda had to procure at a private pharmacy. For a few days, Manuel appeared to be improving, was eating regularly, and was having less frequent and more solid bowel movements. Then, suddenly, Manuel fainted one morning while he was out with Rosalinda on her stoop.

I happened to stop by on the same day to see Rosalinda and to my surprise there was a commotion around her stoop. Rosalinda was holding Manuel and talking loudly to the people gathered around her. Rosalinda was notably incensed, but also looked relieved. As I got closer and joined the conversation, I heard Rosalinda say, “... [Manuel] doubled over just like a ragdoll!” She let her neck and shoulders droop as she said this, to mimic Manuel. Like other days, Rosalinda set-up shop on her stoop before noon, but unlike other days Rosalinda kept

Manuel physically close to her as she did so. Manuel had been running a fever most of the morning and she could not seem to get it down. As she was finally sitting down with Manuel, he suddenly went limp and became unresponsive.

I got really scared and started screaming for someone to help me. People came out to see what was happening and someone said, “Take him to the gringo [medical] brigade down the street.” I just started running down the street, I didn’t even ask anyone to look after my things.

A medical brigade staffed by doctors from the USA had been hosting a temporary open clinic a block away at a local public school. Rosalinda had known about the clinic but did not seem interested in their services, until Manuel collapsed. She continued, “They immediately took Manuel from me and gave him fluids and something for his fever. They even gave me some medicine to take with me. To keep giving him.” Rosalinda continued, “They also have some dentists there. I think I am going to take Carlos, so they can look at his teeth. Why am I going to go all the way to the [CS]? And it’s free. I’m going to take advantage [of the brigade].” Manuel collapsed on a Thursday afternoon and Rosalinda went with Carlos to the Brigade on Saturday. When I talked to Rosalinda about her visit the following week, she told me that the dentist that saw Carlos recommended against extracting the molar and instead treated the cavities. After that, Carlos stopped complaining about tooth aches. From then on, roughly the end of June 2018, Rosalinda sought the advice of either doctor Martín, or a private practice nurse she knew, whenever she or one of her children fell ill. On one occasion, when I asked her about this apparent choice, she said, “Why am I going to go [to the CS]? It's not like they even have any medicine. And just to get treated poorly ... What's the point?” Rosalinda used *treated* in reference to *trato*.

As of April 2019, Rosalinda was suffering from persistent headaches and insomnia, two

conditions she first reported when I started talking with her in April 2018. She also reported high fevers accompanied by diarrhea about once every two months. According to Rosalinda's weekly descriptions, Manuel and Carlos got sick about once month. Carlos most frequently suffered from respiratory tract issues, whereas Manuel usually suffered from diarrhea accompanied by fevers. Sometimes, these health issues would overlap. I always encouraged Rosalinda to seek medical attention at the CS and she always said she would. Then, a couple of days later, she would tell me she was getting some money together to give her private-practice nurse-friend a call. In June 2019, a month after the protests described above, Rosalinda, Manuel and Carlos all became sick. Both Carlos and Manuel had high fevers and coughs with phlegm, and Rosalinda complained of high fevers and general malaise. For all three, Rosalinda opted to go to a private clinic to receive treatment. Her rationale continued to be that it made no sense to use a public health care system that was not capable of dispensing medication nor of allowing her to preserve a sense of personal dignity.

Discussion and Conclusion

To assuage concerns over intended legislative changes, the Minister of Health focused on how employment rights and conditions would remain unaffected, a significant concern within the organized social movement, but hardly the only one. The restructuring of health care services was portrayed as a technical matter that just needed to be understood properly. However, these discussions did not address, or purposefully ignored, poor families' ongoing experiences with public health care services. Within this context, Rosalinda set a claim as an actor shaping a local world through "transcendent, immediate, and 'situated'" choices (Gordon 1995:31): Rosalinda both sought care outside of the public health sector and participated in local protests to protect

her continued access to the public health sector. She had no innate desire to pay for health care services, but the *choice* was increasingly between *not paying* (more) and risking one of her children's lives. The process of creating the conditions necessary for the privatization of the public health care system was literally putting lives at risk, simply demonstrating that the process of accumulation of capital needs to create categories of valuable and non-valuable lives to then exploit that difference to produce value (Bear 2020).

Gordon defined "oppression" as "the imposition of extraordinary conditions of the ordinary upon individuals in the course of their effort to live 'ordinary' lives" (1995:41). Under different conditions of life, Rosalinda's decision to seek private health care services could, maybe, be regarded as nothing more than a preference, but Rosalinda seemed to frame her options in terms of a lesser evil. If the "lived body is the subject of agency" (Gordon 1995:45), Rosalinda was at every moment exercising her agency while choosing between different medical services. However, we need to consider the context within which her "choices" were made and how the "options" available presented themselves (Gordon 1995:31). Rosalinda had, at least, two options: using the public health care system or securing private health care services. However, concealed within these *options* was the very real possibility of death. The type of *option* available to Rosalinda and her children in the public system was one that confronted them with different forms of violence, and which put their life at some risk. Manuel's life was literally in jeopardy. In seeking private services, Rosalinda was *choosing* her *life* and the *lives* of her children (to *not die*), over remaining with the *option* that compromised those *lives*. None-the-less, this *choice* ultimately introduced more precarity into Rosalinda's life as access to these services depended on Rosalinda's ability to purchase them. Honduran health care financing through out-of-pocket expenditures (Toledo-Prieto et al. 2018) meant that Rosalinda was forced

to pay regardless of visiting public or private providers, although the cost was higher with private providers. Rosalinda also began to solicit services from a nurse who worked in a private practice, but whose actual skill and training were unclear and whose services were completely unregulated. Likewise, Rosalinda was forced to rely on other types of non-profit private services that were intermittently available when purchasing was not an option (e.g., the medical brigade referenced above). The medical brigade was able to offer both emergency services and dental care for Rosalinda's children, but the brigade merely supplanted services that should have been provided within a functioning CS and could not address either the need for recurring treatment or the conditions of life that made recurring treatment a necessity; presumably something that can be accomplished within a well-functioning and integrated public health system (Breilh 2013). Following Figueroa and Santos, if the crisis in public health care was indeed orchestrated to facilitate privatization of public services, then Rosalinda's and her children's death would not have necessarily hindered modernization and privatization as these deaths, especially in the aggregate, would have only served to augment the crisis as many other lives already had.

Both Rosalinda's and her children's experiences with health care and their general conditions of life in an inner-city urban margin were slowly structured through several modernizing, restructuring, and adjustment processes, both political and economic, meant to favor capital accumulation. State "abandonment" (Verdugo n.d.:2) of public health care services made it inevitable for Rosalinda to participate within a local private health marketplace. The 30-year history of public health care sector modernization must have produced many other experiences like Rosalinda's that were not considered relevant or meaningful during policy determination or, rather, were made meaningful in a particularly "perverse" way. Total poverty in the country went from 60.2 percent in 2007 (PAHO 2009:9) to 73.6 percent in 2021 (INE

2021:9). Given the concomitant rise of public-private partnerships during this same period (Barahona 2018), it is also difficult to fathom that policy implementers, like the Minister of Health, were unaware of the potential impacts of policies that sought to further decentralize and privatize essential public services like health. The permanence of a system that created the conditions where Rosalinda was forced to make the choice between not using private health care services and risking death would seem to require the existence of institutions, and institutional actors, that deemed the “population at large,” like Rosalinda, as simply an overdetermined mass of agents whose continued oppression was not avoided, or even accidental, in the course of attaining a desired goal, but rather deliberate, strategic, and necessary. Rosalinda’s response to the decrees proposed during 2019, as well as the response coming from other organized public sectors, lends credence to the notion that the Minister’s claims were understood to be empty guarantees or simply lies. Although governmental representatives failed to “construct collectives and norms” to “militate against sociality” (Gordon 1995:22), as evinced by protests and uproar, previous attempts were successful, as evidenced by Rosalinda’s conditions of life, her experiences using public health care services, and her being forced to use private health care services to avoid a premature death.

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Notes

¹ Weekly recurring interviews focused on the same four questions to ascertain illness episodes within the household and household-level responses.

² For a different use of Gordon's (1995) "institutional bad faith" by an anthropologist see Stevenson (2014).

³ Decreto No. 286-2009: Ley para el establecimiento de una Visión de País y la adopción de un Plan de Nación para Honduras. 2 February 2010. Periódico Oficial La Gaceta No. 32,129.

⁴ The decrees in question were 'Law for Budgetary Restructuring and Transformation of the Secretary of State in the Office of Health' and 'Law for Budgetary Restructuring and Transformation of the Secretary of State in the Office of Education.' The protests that followed the initial approval of the decrees in Congress ensured that these were never published in the official Legal Gazette (La Gaceta) and thus never became law.

⁵ The exchange rate at the time: 24.55 Honduran *Lempiras* (Lps.) = 1 US\$

⁶ A common malady reported for young children stemming from, according to Rosalinda, envious wayward glances.

⁷ Local illness associated with a variety of gastrointestinal symptoms (Baer et al. 1998), in Tegucigalpa it was treated with massages and laxatives.

⁸ Someone skilled at performing the massages used to cure *empacho*.

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